

GIS-AHP Analysis of Landslide Conditioning Factors and Susceptibility Zonation in the Thanga Region, Manipur, India

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Abstract

This study applies a Geographic Information System-Analytic Hierarchy Process (GIS-AHP) framework to identify landslide conditioning factors and prepare a susceptibility zonation map for the Thanga region of Manipur, India. Field observations, satellite imagery, Survey of India toposheets, Geological Survey of India sheets and CARTOSAT 10 m DEM data were integrated. Ten factors were used: slope gradient, slope aspect, curvature, lithology, land use/land cover, NDVI, rainfall, elevation, drainage density and distance from road. The layers were prepared in GIS, reclassified, weighted through AHP and combined by weighted overlay. Elevation (19%), slope gradient (16%), slope aspect (16%), rainfall (12%) and distance from road (12%) emerged as the dominant controls. The final map classifies the area into Very Low (39.0%), Low (18.4%), Moderate (14.2%), High (10.7%) and Very High (17.7%) susceptibility; High and Very High classes together cover 29.4%. Field checks show that observed landslide sectors largely coincide with higher-susceptibility terrain, especially near roads, steep slopes, disturbed vegetation and drainage-stressed areas. The GIS-AHP model therefore provides a practical basis for slope monitoring, mitigation and land-use planning in Thanga.

Keywords: Landslide susceptibility; GIS; AHP; remote sensing; hazard zonation; slope instability

1. Introduction

Landslides are persistent geomorphic hazards in hill and mountain regions, particularly where fragile slope materials, intense monsoonal rainfall and expanding human disturbance coincide. Rainwater increases pore water pressure, lowers the effective stress, and causes failure in weathered or overly-steepened slopes (Khan et al., 2025). Susceptibility analysis tackles the spatial aspect regarding how prone a location would be to failure in its present environment (Reichenbach et al., 2018).

The construction of roads usually exacerbates the problem through slope cutting, loss of slope support, changes in the drainage pattern, and the exposure of weathered rock layers (Roy, 2022; Shrestha, 2025). In cases where such conditions are combined with low drainage, clearing of vegetation, and seasonal rainfalls, sectors that are susceptible to landslides become even more localized. The method of susceptibility zonation is hence not only an analysis tool but also a means of segregating stable areas of the terrain from slope sectors which require further attention or remediation (Fell et al., 2008).

GIS and remote sensing now allow topographic, lithological, hydrological, ecological and anthropogenic variables to be assessed within one spatial framework (Metternicht et al., 2005; Tian et al., 2026). AHP remains useful where detailed local knowledge exists but a long landslide inventory is limited, because it converts expert judgement into transparent factor weights (Saaty, 1987; Morales & de Vries, 2021). This article identifies the main conditioning factors in Thanga, applies GIS-AHP weighting, and evaluates whether high-susceptibility sectors correspond with field-observed landslide locations.

2. Study Area

2.1 Location and terrain setting

The study area is the Thanga region of Manipur, India, represented by a 5.6 km² mapped polygon extending from 24°31'00"N to 24°33'00"N and 93°48'00"E to 93°50'00"E, with an approximate centroid near 24°32'00"N, 93°49'00"E. Elevation ranges from 715 m to 846 m above mean sea level and falls on Survey of India toposheet

83H/14 (Fig. 1). The area is treated as a landslide-prone hill environment where steep terrain, weathered materials, seasonal rainfall, drainage concentration and human modification interact.

Fig 1: Geographic context and mapped extent of the Thanga study area (24°31'00"N–24°33'00"N; 93°48'00"E–93°50'00"E).

2.2 Geological/lithological and drainage setting

The broader geological setting is associated with the Disang and Upper Disang formations. For the susceptibility model, lithology is the operational variable: shale, siltstone, greywacke rhythmite and sandstone dominate the mapped area. These materials differ in weathering behaviour and resistance, so lithology affects how strongly rainfall reduces slope strength.

Drainage also contributes to instability. A moderate to high drainage density reflects areas of potential concentration of surface water and underground flows.

2.3 Climate, land use, and landslide setting

The climatic regime is monsoonal, with the highest landslide sensitivity during June-September. Rainfall directly affects the mechanical behaviour of weathered soils and clay-rich slope materials, while orographic effects may strengthen rainfall impacts at higher terrain positions.

Land use and vegetation condition add an anthropogenic dimension. Field observations indicate that many failures occur close to roads where slopes have been cut, drainage is poor and vegetation has been disturbed. Thanga is therefore best understood as a monsoonal hill landscape shaped by both natural predisposition and human modification.

3. Data and Methods

3.1 Data sources

The analysis integrates field observations and geospatial datasets for the 5.6 km² Thanga polygon. Spatial preprocessing, raster reclassification, weighted overlay and cartographic layout were undertaken in a GIS environment using a projected reference system for distance and area operations. Primary inputs comprised field survey observations, satellite imagery, Survey of India toposheets, Geological Survey of India sheets and CARTOSAT 10 m DEM data. The original GIS workspace should be checked before submission for exact imagery dates, rainfall data period, processing settings and software version.

Table 1. Data sources and their analytical role in the Thanga GIS-AHP study.

Data source	Nature of input	Primary analytical role
Field survey	Ground observations	Validation of landslide-affected sectors and interpretation of local slope conditions
Satellite imagery	Remote sensing imagery	Preparation and interpretation of LULC, NDVI, and general surface condition
Survey of India toposheets	Cartographic/topographic base	Topographic reference, drainage interpretation, and base mapping support

Geological Survey of India sheets	Geological mapping input	Lithological and geological context for slope-material characterization
CARTOSAT 10 m DEM	Elevation raster	Derivation of slope, aspect, curvature, and elevation layers for terrain analysis
QGIS 4.0.0	GIS software environment	Spatial preprocessing, raster reclassification, weighted overlay analysis, and final cartographic layout

3.2 Selection of conditioning factors

Ten conditioning factors were selected: slope gradient, slope aspect, curvature, lithology, land use/land cover, NDVI, rainfall, elevation, drainage density and distance from road. This set captures relief, terrain orientation, surface form, substrate, vegetation condition, hydrological triggering and road-related disturbance, which are the main process groups relevant to Thanga.

The DEM-derived variables represent complementary topographic controls. Slope gradient measures gravitational stress; aspect influences moisture, solar exposure and vegetation; curvature identifies concave, convex and planar surfaces that affect runoff concentration; and elevation marks the terrain belt where observed instability is concentrated.

The remaining variables represent material, ecological, hydrological and anthropogenic controls. Lithology expresses rock and weathered-mantle resistance; LULC and NDVI indicate surface cover and vegetation condition; rainfall represents the principal trigger; drainage density captures flow concentration; and distance from road identifies slope cutting, toe removal and drainage disruption.

Table 2. Landslide conditioning factors and their process relevance in the Thanga region.

Conditioning factor	Category	Process relevance
Slope gradient	Topographic	Controls gravitational stress and slope instability threshold
Slope aspect	Topographic	Influences moisture retention, weathering, and vegetation regime
Curvature	Topographic	Represents local flow concentration and breaks of slope
Lithology	Material	Reflects erosional resistance and mechanical weakness of slope materials
LULC	Surface/anthropogenic	Captures vegetation cover, built-up land, and disturbed surfaces
NDVI	Ecological	Indicates vegetation density/health and root reinforcement potential
Rainfall	Hydro-climatic	Represents the principal monsoonal trigger of landslides
Elevation	Topographic	Marks terrain position and the main instability belt
Drainage density	Hydrological	Represents runoff concentration and pore-pressure buildup potential
Distance from road	Anthropogenic	Captures cut-slope disturbance, toe removal, and drainage disruption

3.3 Preparation of thematic layers

Thematic layers were prepared according to the analytical role of each factor. Slope, aspect, curvature and elevation were derived from the CARTOSAT 10 m DEM. Slope was grouped into five classes from 0-3.6° to 30-57°, with steeper classes treated as more susceptible because they operate closer to instability thresholds.

Aspect was divided into flat and compass-direction classes; north and northeast slopes were interpreted as more susceptible because they retain more moisture. Curvature was classified as concave, flat and convex, distinguishing areas of water accumulation from breaks of slope where shallow failure may initiate.

Elevation was retained as a major terrain-position variable. The mapped classes range from 720-730 m to 810-850 m, while field observations locate the broader failure belt within 700-1000 m. In this setting, elevation marks the zone where slope steepness, weathered materials and monsoonal saturation overlap.

Lithology, LULC and NDVI were prepared to represent material resistance and surface protection. Shale-, siltstone- and greywacke-dominated sectors were considered more failure-prone. Open forest can moderate runoff and reinforce shallow slopes, whereas built-up, transport-related and barren surfaces increase disturbance and runoff concentration. Low NDVI indicates weaker vegetation and reduced root cohesion.

Rainfall, drainage density and distance from road complete the factor set. Rainfall was reclassified into five classes from 1582-1586 mm to 1600-1604 mm. Drainage density was classified from very low to very high. Road-distance buffers at 20, 50, 80, 110 and 450 m represent decreasing road-cut influence with distance.

Table 3. Representative class breaks and thematic categories used in the susceptibility model.

Factor	Classes / categories	Interpretive note
Slope gradient	0–3.6; 3.7–11; 12–19; 20–29; 30–57°	Higher classes represent steeper and less stable terrain
Slope aspect	Flat; N; NE; E; SE; S; SW; W; NW; N	N/NE sectors more susceptible
Curvature	Concave; Flat; Convex	Controls runoff concentration
Lithology	Shale, siltstone, greywacke rhythmite & sandstone; undifferentiated fluvial sediments	Fine-grained units more weathering-prone
LULC	Aquaculture; Lakes/Pond; Open Forest; Transport Network; Built-Up	Disturbed surfaces indicate higher susceptibility
NDVI	Very healthy vegetation; Moderately healthy vegetation; Unhealthy vegetation; Non vegetation	Lower cover means weaker root reinforcement
Rainfall	1582–1586; 1587–1591; 1592–1595; 1596–1599; 1600–1604 mm	Higher classes increase saturation
Elevation	720–730; 740–750; 760–780; 790–800; 810–850 m	Main failure belt broadly within 700–1000 m
Drainage density	Very Low; Low; Moderate; High; Very High	Higher concentration increases instability
Distance from road	20; 50; 80; 110; 450 m	Near-road cut slopes most susceptible

GIS-AHP analytical workflow

Fig 3: GIS-AHP analytical workflow used to derive landslide susceptibility zonation for the Thanga region.

3.4 AHP weighting

AHP was used to assign relative influence to the ten factors through pairwise comparison and factor prioritisation. The final weights were elevation 19%, slope gradient 16%, slope aspect 16%, rainfall 12%, distance from road 12%, drainage density 9%, LULC 8%, lithology 4%, NDVI 3% and curvature 2%. This hierarchy indicates that terrain position and slope form dominate susceptibility, while rainfall and road disturbance intensify local instability.

Table 4. AHP weights of the major conditioning factors used in the susceptibility model.

Rank	Conditioning factor	Weight (%)
1	Elevation	19
2	Slope gradient	16
3	Slope aspect	16
4	Rainfall	12
5	Distance from road	12
6	Drainage density	9
7	LULC	8
8	Lithology	4
9	NDVI	3
10	Curvature	2

3.5 Weighted overlay and zonation

The reclassified thematic layers were integrated through GIS weighted overlay. Each factor layer was standardised into susceptibility-relevant classes and combined according to its AHP weight, producing a composite susceptibility surface that reflects the cumulative effect of terrain, material, vegetation, drainage, rainfall and road disturbance.

The composite output was divided into five susceptibility classes. Although the source map uses risk-zone terminology, the journal text uses Very Low, Low, Moderate, High and Very High susceptibility because the model maps relative landslide predisposition rather than full risk, which would also require exposure and vulnerability assessment.

This distinction is important: the map shows where conditioning factors converge, not when a slope will fail.

3.6 Validation approach

Validation was based on field-grounded correspondence between mapped susceptibility classes and observed landslide-affected sectors. A field inventory of three major landslide stations was overlaid on the final zonation. These sites occur mainly within High and Very High susceptibility classes and are associated with slopes generally exceeding 30°, short road distance, disturbed cut slopes, poor local drainage, weathered soil and vegetation disturbance.

4. Results

4.1 Spatial pattern of conditioning factors

The thematic maps show that landslide susceptibility in Thanga is produced by the convergence of steep topography, moisture-sensitive aspect, weak materials, monsoonal rainfall, drainage concentration, vegetation disturbance and road-related slope modification. Slope gradient is a clear control: about 35-40% of the area lies in steeper categories, and the principal landslide stations occur on slopes greater than 30°. Such slopes need only additional saturation, toe cutting or drainage concentration to fail.

Aspect and curvature refine this pattern. North- and northeast-facing slopes are more moisture-retentive, while concave surfaces can concentrate water and colluvium. Convex breaks of slope may also mark shallow failure initiation points. Although curvature has the smallest AHP weight, it helps explain local variation within the broader slope-elevation framework.

Elevation is the strongest factor because observed failures cluster within the 700-1000 m belt, where steep slopes, weathered materials, monsoonal rainfall and vegetation loss coincide. Lithology reinforces this pattern: shale, siltstone and greywacke rhythmite are more susceptible where weathering and saturation reduce material strength.

LULC and NDVI indicate that surface condition is part of the susceptibility mechanism. Open forest provides some runoff moderation and root reinforcement, whereas built-up, transport-related and barren surfaces tend to concentrate runoff and expose slopes to disturbance. Low NDVI areas therefore indicate sectors where shallow slope stability is weaker.

Rainfall, drainage density and road proximity complete the instability structure. Rainfall triggers saturation during the monsoon; drainage density identifies zones of concentrated flow and pore-pressure build-up; and distance from road captures the effect of slope cutting and drainage disruption. The observation that many failures occur within 20-100 m of roads is particularly important because it identifies road-adjacent steep terrain as a priority planning concern.

DEM-derived conditioning factors

Fig 4: DEM-derived conditioning factors: (a) slope gradient, (b) slope aspect, (c) curvature, and (d) elevation.

Surface and material conditioning factors

Fig 5: Surface and material conditioning factors: (a) lithology, (b) land use/land cover, and (c) NDVI.

Fig 6: Triggering and anthropogenic conditioning factors: (a) rainfall, (b) drainage density, and (c) distance from road.

4.2 Relative factor influence

The AHP ranking converts these spatial patterns into a clear hierarchy. Elevation receives the highest weight (19%), followed by slope gradient and slope aspect (16% each). Rainfall and distance from road each receive 12%, while drainage density, LULC, lithology, NDVI and curvature act as secondary but meaningful modifiers.

This ranking is operationally useful because it separates first-order controls from local modifiers. Topography creates the basic predisposition to failure; rainfall, drainage and road disturbance determine where that predisposition becomes most acute.

4.3 Susceptibility zonation

The final weighted overlay classifies the Thanga region into Very Low (39.0%), Low (18.4%), Moderate (14.2%), High (10.7%) and Very High (17.7%) susceptibility classes. The High and Very High classes together cover 29.4% of the mapped area, indicating that nearly one-third of the terrain requires stronger caution in land-use and slope-management decisions.

The highest classes correspond with steep slopes, short distance from roads, disturbed surfaces, drainage concentration and field-observed instability. The map therefore represents where multiple conditioning factors combine to produce the greatest likelihood of landslide occurrence.

Because the hotspot footprint is not limited to isolated points, mitigation should be planned at the scale of road corridors, slope clusters and development zones rather than only at individual failure sites.

Table 5. Area distribution across the final susceptibility classes.

Susceptibility class	Area share (%)	Interpretive significance
Very Low	39.0	Terrain with comparatively limited landslide predisposition under the mapped conditions
Low	18.4	Relatively stable sectors requiring routine observation
Moderate	14.2	Transitional terrain where local disturbance can increase instability
High	10.7	Priority sectors for slope monitoring and mitigation planning
Very High	17.7	Most unstable terrain where multiple conditioning factors converge

High + Very High	29.4	Combined hotspot footprint requiring the strongest risk-sensitive planning
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Fig 7: Final landslide susceptibility zonation map derived from the primary GIS analysis.

4.4 Validation of zonation

Validation shows meaningful correspondence between the GIS-AHP output and ground evidence. The three major landslide stations fall within higher-susceptibility terrain, especially where steep slopes, roads and disturbed vegetation coincide. This supports the model as a tool for monitoring and mitigation priorities.

The validation remains qualitative because the inventory is small. A larger landslide inventory, class-wise success-rate table and independent validation dataset would strengthen future work. Even so, the observed match between landslide-affected sectors and High/Very High classes supports the map as a local screening tool.

5. Discussion

The dominance of elevation, slope gradient and aspect confirms that terrain organisation is the primary control on landslide susceptibility in Thanga. Elevation identifies the instability belt, slope gradient controls gravitational stress, and aspect structures moisture retention and vegetation behaviour. These variables define the landscape's basic predisposition to failure.

Monsoonal rains and road cut make it more likely for certain pre-disposed slopes to turn out as instable. Rain increases pore pressure due to saturation of soil pores while road cut destabilizes slope through drainage interference. This finding is consistent with wider susceptibility research, which emphasises the combined role of topography, materials, rainfall, land cover and human disturbance (Ayalew & Yamagishi, 2005; Guzzetti et al., 1999; Reichenbach et al., 2018; van Westen et al., 2003; Shano et al., 2020).

A central contribution of the study is therefore the demonstration that landslides in Thanga arise from interacting natural and anthropogenic controls. Steep slopes, weak lithology, concentrated drainage and monsoonal rainfall create sensitivity; road cuts, vegetation loss and poor drainage convert that sensitivity into local instability.

The planning implications are direct. High-susceptibility road segments should be prioritised for retaining structures, toe protection, catch drains, culvert maintenance, bioengineering, revegetation and restrictions on unregulated slope cutting. The map can also guide community awareness and monsoon-season monitoring.

The main limitations are methodological transparency and validation depth. Before final submission, the AHP pairwise matrix, lambda max, consistency index and consistency ratio should be reported; imagery dates and rainfall-source periods should be specified; and the three landslide stations should be documented in a class-wise validation table. These additions would improve reproducibility without changing the main conclusion.

6. Conclusion

This study used a GIS-AHP framework to analyse landslide conditioning factors and prepare a susceptibility zonation map for the Thanga region of Manipur. Ten factors were integrated: slope gradient, slope aspect, curvature, lithology, LULC, NDVI, rainfall, elevation, drainage density and distance from road. Elevation, slope gradient, slope aspect, rainfall and distance from road were the dominant controls, showing that susceptibility is governed by terrain position, terrain form, monsoonal rainfall and road-related disturbance.

The final map shows that 29.4% of the area falls within High and Very High susceptibility classes. These zones correspond with steep slopes, road proximity, disturbed or deforested surfaces, concentrated drainage and observed landslide occurrence. The model therefore captures the main geography of slope instability in Thanga and provides a usable spatial basis for hazard-informed planning.

The study contributes a field-supported example of landslide susceptibility assessment in a monsoonal hill landscape of Northeast India. With complete AHP reporting, verified data metadata and a stronger validation appendix, the manuscript would be ready for submission to a geomorphology, engineering-geology or applied GIS journal.

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